

Supplementary Figure 5

Supplementary Fig. 5. Quantitative analysis of miR-155 in situ hybridization in the rat TLE model showed increased miR-155 expression in the dentate gyrus (DG; **A**, acute stage $p < 0.05$, chronic stage $p < 0.01$), CA1 area (**B**, acute stage $p < 0.05$, chronic stage $p < 0.05$), and entorhinal cortex (EC) (**C**, acute stage $p < 0.05$, chronic stage $p < 0.01$); Mann-Whitney U test, error bars depict the standard error of the mean.